

ELECTRONS IMAGING OF MOLECULES IN DGEBA-CARBON FIBERS COMPOSITES

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The feasibility of electrons molecular imaging in glassy polymers is discussed first. Tilted dark-field mode of electron microscope is then definitely chosen for studying ultra-microtome thin-sections of amorphous DGEBA polymers. DGEBA was cured either by DDA or DDS in various conditions. The fibers included were high modulus "graphite" (Serofim AG) and high tensile strength carbon (Serofim AXT and Torray 300). In the absence of strains the molecules obey the random coil model. Bisphenol A groups, distributed at random in the polymer, are individually visible in the dark-field images as bright elongated units 10 Å to 5 Å in size. The thin-sections are entirely homogeneous both in bright and dark-field. However, electrons irradiation in a poor vacuum is responsible for the early occurrence of nodules (~ 100 Å). The local order thus slightly improves as the bisphenol A groups tend to join end to end and also to align in parallel. Progressive etching causes the occurrence of microvoids, in increasing number and size. The thin-sections then deform and fail by a crazing process. Thin interfaces of 1 or 2 layers of bisphenol A groups, are produced in high-tensile-strength fiber composites. On the contrary, adhesion is purely physical in high modulus "graphite" fiber composites.

The mechanical properties of carbon-fiber-glass-epoxy composites depend on the structure and the microtexture of the fiber and the polymer and of the nature of the interfaces as well. The final aim when studying composites, is to determine their aging mechanism, i.e their serviceability according to environmental conditions. Any data on composites microstructures can thus be used to achieve such a purpose. For characterizing composites, dark-field high resolution microscopy was chosen, since it has been recently improved, first by applying to polyaromatic structure imaging [1,2,3], then by amorphous compounds studies [4]. For reliably interpreting electron images in terms of molecular imaging, the object has to be thin (for both reducing inelastic scattering and for using the phase-object approximation). The electron microscope techniques have thus to be optimized [5].

1 - METHODS OF PREPARATION

Thin-sections were cut with an ultra-microtome, equipped with a diamond knife and only the thinnest ones were selected for study. They were picked-up on microgrids, made of holey carbon films [6]. The sections are thus self sustained over large enough regions to be observed. The samples here studied are ten DGEBA amine cured epoxies, prepared by E. Morel at IRCHA and S. Michel-Dansac at CdF Chimie, in various conditions (various proportions, curing temperatures, residence times and curing agents). In addition to bulk polymers, various carbon fibers were included in a DGEBA matrix (high modulus "graphite" fibers : Serofim AG and high tensile strength carbon fibers : Serofim AXT and Toray 300). Composites were also prepared by thin-sectioning.

2 - ELECTRON MICROSCOPY TECHNIQUES

Electrons scattering occurs under the incident beam impingement when atoms are ordered in the object, even in a short range ; i.e atomic interferences are produced. The smallest the number of identical interatomic distances, the broadest and the less numerous the scattered beams. For instance, very intense and relatively sharp Debye-Scherrer rings are given by polyaromatic molecules which only contain a few aromatic rings, while diffuse and dim haloes are given by glassy polymers. Each haloe is not distinct from the other and since their radius is small, they are hidden by inelastic scattering. In the electron microscope the diffraction pattern (SAD pattern) is formed in the back focal plane of the objective lens A (Fig. 1). By comparison to X-ray

Figure 1 : Ray path for a convergent lens

diffraction patterns, various peaks can be recognized for epoxies, despite the poor appearance of the SAD patterns. The peak positions and relative intensities can be plotted versus the scattering vector $|\vec{s}|$, chosen as the abscissa (Fig. 2b).

$$|\vec{s}|_{\text{\AA}^{-1}} = \frac{2 \sin \theta}{\lambda} = \frac{1}{d}; \lambda \text{ the wave-length being small } (|\vec{s}| \sim \frac{2\theta}{\lambda}) \quad (1)$$

For 100 KeV (EM 300 Philips electron microscope) or 120 KeV (EM 400 Philips) λ varies from 0.037 Å to 0.033 Å; the scattering angle 2θ is thus smaller than one or two degrees. By using $|\vec{s}|$ as a variable, the data are independent of λ and thus of the microscope used. Comparison between Figure 2b and Figure 3b shows that no noticeable scattering can be found beyond 0.65 \AA^{-1} , around the undeviated transmitted beam 000. Three peaks appears respectively at about 0.21 \AA^{-1} , 0.28 \AA^{-1} and 0.46 \AA^{-1} , which are thus the radius of 3 Debye-Scherrer rings.

Figure 2 : a. Transfer function for optimum bright field ;
b. Schematic diffraction pattern of DGEBA polymer.

In the electron microscope (Fig. 1) the enlarged optical image is formed in the Gaussian plane G of the objective lens, where all the beams transmitted through the object interfere. Projection lenses are used only for magnifying, either the pattern A, or the image G, on the observation screen. In order to obtain an accurate representation of the atomic structure of the object, i.e suitable for molecular imaging, the beams have to keep their initial phases when interfering, i.e their phases when leaving the object. Unfortunately, the objective lens have a spherical aberration C_s , which cannot be corrected. It leads to an increasing phase-shift as the scattering angle 2θ increases. This phase-shift added to that introduced by the defocussing of the objective lens Δf_0 , according to Eq. (2), gives a total phase-shift χ [7]

$$\chi = \frac{\pi}{2} - \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} C_s \frac{(2\theta)^4}{4} + \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \Delta f_0 \frac{(2\theta)^2}{2} \quad (2)$$

For obtaining bright-field accurate images, with a maximum contrast, Δf_0 has to be chosen in order to have $\cos \chi = \pm 1$ (or, at least ± 0.7 which is the minimum acceptable value for the contrast). Figure 2a shows the variation of $\cos \chi$ in the case of the EM 300, operating at 100 kV, for $C_s = 1.6 \text{ mm}$ and $\Delta f_0 = 800 \text{ \AA}$ (underfocussing) [8]. This corresponds to the optimum conditions for bright-field, i.e no phase-shift is introduced by the lens for all the beams situated between 0.10 \AA^{-1} and 0.25 \AA^{-1} . Beyond this value the lens introduces random phase-shifts in the beams responsible for noise, which destroys the image accuracy.

The scattered beams situated in this region have to be eliminated by an aperture (objective aperture), 0.25 \AA^{-1} in radius, set in the back focal plane of the lens (hachured in Fig. 2a,b). The lens also introduces phase-shifts in the region between 0 and 0.10 \AA^{-1} , around the optical axis of the lens A. If some scattered beams are in this region, they are not in phase, but they cannot however be eliminated. The inelastic electrons also are detrimental to the image contrast since they are at their maximum intensity in this region. Additionally a comparison between Figure 2a and b shows that bright-field imaging should not be used for epoxies-imaging, since about half of the scattered beams would not contribute to the image formation while the beams existing between 0 and 0.10 \AA^{-1} would spoil the image.

In the high-resolution tilted dark-field mode, the objective aperture is left centered in A, but the incident beam is tilted relatively to the lens optical axis, to eliminate the unscattered 000 beam from the aperture opening (Fig. 3). If a suitable point of the diffraction pattern is brought to coincide with the optical axis of the lens A, the object regions which issue the beams selected by the aperture opening, will thus appear bright on a dark-field. Since the unscattered transmitted beam is missing, the optimum conditions for imaging correspond to $\cos \chi = 0$ (or ± 0.3) [9], i.e. no additional phase-shifts are introduced between the scattered waves. Figure 3a shows that this condition is fulfilled on both sides of A, in the whole range from 0 to 0.21 \AA^{-1} , i.e. in a 0.42 \AA^{-1} range, when $\Delta f_0 = 400 \text{ \AA}$ (underfocussing). Though the maximum possible $|\cos \chi|$ value is 0.21 \AA^{-1} instead of 0.25 \AA^{-1} , an area practically double in size can be used in the pattern (0.42 \AA^{-1}). Figure 3b shows that practically all the beams scattered by DGEBA contribute to form the image, without parasitic phase-shifts, when the aperture centered in A is 0.21 \AA^{-1} in radius (Fig. 3a) and when the pattern point corresponding to A is 0.32 \AA^{-1} . For such an aperture the resolving power is better than 4 \AA .

Figure 3 : a. Transfer function for optimum tilted dark-field ;
b. Schematic diffraction pattern with suitable tilting of the 000 beam.

For studying composites instead of bulk-polymers alone, both polymer and carbon fibers have to light-up. Another dark-field technique has thus to be used [10]. The more intense beam emitted by fibers is the 002 beam, scattered by the aromatic layer planes (next to 0.3 \AA^{-1}). The two others, respectively situated at 0.47 \AA^{-1} and 0.81 \AA^{-1} , have to be eliminated for obtaining understandable images. Fortunately the more intense beam of DGEBA is close to 0.22 \AA^{-1} , i.e. very close to 002. Hence an aperture 0.1 \AA^{-1} in radius is suitable to let through both 002 of carbon and the DGEBA scattered beam, while it eliminates 10 and 11 of carbon. The carbon fiber and the matrix thus light-on altogether

when the pattern point corresponding to A is 0.23 \AA^{-1} . However the resolving power is noticeably reduced ($\sim 8 \text{ \AA}$).

3 - MOLECULAR IMAGING OF DGEBA

The photo 1a, plate I shows that many diffracting units are bright spikes (see for instance insert in 1a). Their length is about 10 \AA and their width about half. The more intense rods are parallel to OA (Fig. 4), the scattering vector which passes through the aperture center. The less visible spikes, and also the less numerous, range around a $\pm 25^\circ$ misorientation. Whatever the aperture opening, the DGEBA diffraction pattern

Figure 4 : Relative positions of the pattern and the objective aperture.

entirely passes through, along OA only. The more oblique relatively to OA the scattering vector, the more the pattern escapes the opening (Fig. 4). The diffracting domains elongated along OA are thus the highest in intensity and in accuracy and are thus seen preferentially. This purely geometrical effect is responsible for the apparent preferred orientation of most of the bright spikes parallel to OA. The absence of parallel preferred orientation of the diffracting domains is confirmed by a rotation of \vec{s} . When it is brought perpendicular to OA by a suitable tilting of the incident beam, the elongated bright domains also turn 90° and appear to remain parallel to \vec{s} . Besides spikes, many isometric units ($\sim 5 \text{ \AA}$) and all the intermediates can be seen in the dark-field images (1a, pl. I). This suggests that elongated parts of molecules are distributed at random in the polymer thin-section, i.e oriented more or less obliquely relatively to

the observation plane. A dark-field micrograph such as 1a, plate I can be used as an object for obtaining its optical Fraunhofer diffraction pattern. It is set slightly beyond the object focal plane of a convergent lens and a laser beam ($\lambda = 6328 \text{ \AA}$) falls upon it at normal incidence. The diffraction pattern is formed in the back focal plane of the lens, which allows to evaluate the size and the shape of the bright domains and their periodicity as well, if any. Photo 1c, plate I shows an anisotropic small angle scattering around the central peak, elongated perpendicularly to the bright spikes in 1a. This confirms their rod-shape. The size of the average unit, evaluated from 1c, well agrees with that evaluated from 1a ($\sim 10 \text{ \AA}$ by 5 \AA). Since no periodicity appears in 1c, the bright domains in 1a are thus distributed at random in the micrograph. Photo 1b, plate I is a model of DGEBA molecule. It shows the occurrence of relatively rigid bisphenol A groups (see the box in 1b), made of two phenyls, connected by a dimethylmethane group. Bisphenol A groups distributed at random in a thin-section, should give in dark-field images bright rods, about 10 \AA by 5 \AA in size, turning progressively to isometric domains about 5 \AA in diameter, since they are increasingly tilted relatively to the observation plane. This strongly suggests that the bright domains, visible in dark-field images, are bisphenol A groups imaging.

4 - NODULAR TEXTURE

Strain corrosion is responsible for glass-epoxy fatigue and failure which strongly affect the behaviour of composite materials. The microscopic failure process is supposed to be due to inhomogeneities at a molecular level, such as nodular texture, i.e regions having a local higher order than the bulk. These regions ($\sim 100 \text{ \AA}$ in size) are supposed to remain intact as the strains apply, forming a resistant network of crosslinked molecular domains. In between these domains, microvoids occur in increasing number, which first coalesce, then grow to occupy most of the glass-polymer volume (phase inversion). Crazes finally appear, develop and the polymer fails [1]. The preceding data show that freshly prepared DGEBA glass does not show any heterogeneity and remains stable when observed in a clean vacuum ($10^{-6} - 10^{-7}$ torr) (EM 400 is equipped with ionic pumping system). However, if observed in a poorer vacuum ($10^{-4} - 10^{-5}$ torr in EM 300) the electrons irradiation etches the sample. Progressively, nodules about 100 \AA in size first appear, then microvoids of the same size form, multiply and enlarge. Finally crazes occur and the polymer fails (photos 2a,b, pl. I). Molecular imaging of DGEBA is noticeably modified by the occurrence of nodules. Quite often, the diffracting bisphenol A domains

are associated end to end (total length superior to $15-20 \text{ \AA}$). Bisphenol A diffracting units also tend to be associated irregularly, by 3 to 9, with a reduced misorientation range ($\sim 10^\circ$). In each nodule, the distance between bright rods fluctuates around 5 \AA . Optical diffraction patterns also change (photo 2c, pl. I). The central diffusion peak remains anisotropic but more obviously. It has the same length as in 1c, plate I but half its width. Measurements in the patterns thus lead to bright rods double in length in keeping the same width (i.e. $\sim 20 \text{ \AA}$ and 5 \AA). Here also the values found for average sizes well agree with dark-field data.

5 - COMPOSITES

Carbon fibers are always made of sheets of aromatic layers stacked in parallel. These sheets are very distorted and folded [3] in such a manner that folds are roughly parallel to the fiber axis. It results in pores elongated along this axis. The microtexture of high modulus "graphite" fibers has been determined by Molleyre et al [12] and described as lamellar [3]. The model of Figure 5 shows that the curvature radius of the layers progressively decreases from the periphery to the center of the fiber.

Figure 5 : High modulus "graphite" fiber model

A majority of layers is then parallel to the external part of the fiber, while in the center, all the possible orientations can be found. Though homogeneous, such a texture helps to understand why so many erroneous models of fiber have been proposed assuming the existence of a skin (layers parallel to the fiber surface) and of a core (radial layers). If high tensile strength carbon fibers are compared to high modulus ones, they only differ by the radius of curvature of their layers which considerably decreases. The number of layers oriented edge-on relatively to the fiber surface, i.e. accessible by their edges, widely increases. When the characteristics of the fiber surface is changed, differences appear in the interfaces between fibers and polymer. Photos 3a,b, plate II show the high modulus "graphite" fiber-DGEBA interface in bright-field and in dark-field. Neither thick, nor thin interface is visible and both the fiber and the polymer images look as expected, i.e. as they are when studied alone. However, the polymer sticks to the carbon layer stacks strongly enough to induce decohesions inside the fiber, rather than in the polymer. These data imply a physical adhesion between the fiber and the polymer. On the contrary thin interfaces develop at the polymer edges and are visible as bright rims in photos 4a and b, pl. II).

Dark-field images 4a,b show the interface between Serofim AXI and epoxy polymer. The scattering vector \vec{s} is 90° rotated from a to b and the elongation axis of the bisphenol A groups as well. An intense bright rim appears along the edges 90° rotated from a to b. A thin layer of bisphenol A groups has thus formed in the polymer at the interface (arrows in 4a,b). Firm conclusions cannot be drawn from such results since the exact aging stage of the above described composites is not known. The respective effect of nature of the fiber surface and of the environmental conditions cannot be thus clearly separated.

The structure of bulk amorphous polymers has been discussed for long and is still debated nowadays. Some authors assume a nodular microstructure with local orientation [13 to 18], while the others propose a disordered microstructure (random coil model) [19 to 21]. In fact none of these assumptions is based on high resolution electron microscopy, since the image conditions have never been calculated or even discussed. The above results show that the random coil model proposed by Flory [20] can be adopted, since no ordered regions are visible in the fresh thin-sections. In fact, the diffracting domains are very small. They represent the rigid part of the DGEBA molecules (bisphenol A groups) distributed at random in the bulk polymer. On the contrary, nodular texture is formed secondarily. It is due to the strains caused by etching of the material. The stresses thus cause the molecules to stretch in the nodules, in such a way that the bisphenol A groups tend to place end to end. They also acquire a tendency to become parallel inside a nodule. This result could appear important for studying the serviceability of the composites in various environmental conditions. The nature of the interface between fibers and polymer should also be profitably used for explaining the mechanism of composites aging. The type of interface entirely depends on the type of the carbon fiber since the reactivity of the carbon layer planes is negligible, while that of the edges is tremendously high. This results in a very low surface reactivity in the case of high modulus fibers (majority of layers parallel to the surface) and in a very high surface reactivity in the case of high tensile strength fibers (majority of layers perpendicular to the surface). The smallest the radius of curvature of the layers, the highest the reactivity. These data well agree with a physical adhesion in the case of high modulus "graphite" fibers and suggest the formation of a thin interface of oriented bisphenol A groups in the case of high tensile strength carbon fibers.

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PLANCHE I

Photo 1 : a. Tilted dark-field of DGEBA polymer ; b. Model of the molecule ;
c. Optical diffraction pattern of a.

Photo 2 : a and b. Nodular microstructures formed by electrons irradiation ;
c. Optical diffraction pattern of b.

PLANCHE II

Photo 3 : DGEBA composite with high modulus fiber ; a. bright-field ;
b. dark-field.

Photo 4 : DGEBA composite with high tensile strength fiber (Serofim AXT).
The diffusion vector turned 90° from a to b.